

RMK LAB

Environmental DNA & Sequencing Protocol Book

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Prepared for RMK Lab student training and protocol continuity

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INTRODUCTION

This protocol book is intended to serve as a practical guide for RMK Lab students carrying out DNA isolation, amplicon library preparation, and Illumina MiSeq sequencing workflows. It is designed especially for new students who are learning to handle environmental samples, prepare DNA extracts, build sequencing libraries, and maintain accurate records throughout the process.

The RMK Lab works with a variety of environmental sample types, including lake-water filters, Sterivex filters, large-volume filtered samples, mats, sediments, and archived DNA extracts. Many of these samples are low-biomass, difficult to replace, or part of long-term Antarctic field projects. For this reason, careful sample tracking, contamination control, and documentation are just as important as following the technical steps of each protocol.

This manual brings together protocols adapted from the RMK Lab, the C. Takacs-Vesbach laboratory at the University of New Mexico, and the Miami University Center for Bioinformatics and Functional Genomics. It includes DNA extraction protocols for Sterivex filters and large-volume filters, RMK-specific Nextera-style amplicon sequencing protocols, CBFG MiSeq/EMP-style sequencing guidance, equipment protocols, and supplies lists. Several protocols include RMK-specific notes, optional stopping points, and troubleshooting comments based on prior lab experience. For example, the Sterivex and large-volume DNA extraction protocols are both two-day phenol-chloroform-based workflows with optional stopping points, while the Nextera protocol is organized as a multi-day sequencing workflow beginning with sample-sheet preparation and ending with MiSeq loading and run setup.

Invitrogen E-Gel Protocol for E-Gel EX agarose gels

(3/9/2024, RMK) ("Baby Gels")

Sample preparation:

Note: The optimal DNA amount for the E-Gel EX agarose gels (which have high sensitivity Sybr Green dye in them) is 0.5 – 50 ng.

1. Dilute your samples with nanopore water: 5 ng/ul is a good concentration for PCR products.
2. Combine your desired volume of sample with 0.1X E-Gel Sample Loading Buffer to bring all samples to a final volume of 20 uL (note, do not use 1X Loading Buffer with the EX gels)
3. Combined 2 uL of E-gel DNA ladder with 18 uL 0.1X E-Gel Sample Loading Buffer
4. For steps #2 and #3, you can use a piece of parfilm to mix your samples/ladder with the loading buffer.

Example of several dilutions of 3 samples on the left and the ladder on the right.
Note: all have a total volume of 20 uL.

5. Remove the gel from its package. Gently remove the comb. Remove the camera (if attached) and open the electrophoresis device lid. Load the gel into the electrophoresis device with the loading lanes at the top.

An example of an E-Gel EX 1% agarose loaded into the electrophoresis device.

6. Load the diluted ladder into the far left lane marked "M".
7. Load your diluted samples into lanes 1 -20. If there are empty lanes, load 20uL of 0.1X loading buffer into them. Close the lid.
8. Set up the run by selecting the correct E-Gel protocol. Choose a run time of 10 mins.
9. Check on your run in real time by turning on the Back light. Samples can be viewed within one minute of starting run.
10. When the run is over, if an image is desired, attach camera and follow instructions to take an image.

An example gel when imaged with the camera.

Three samples were run at concentrations of 5 ng, 15 ng and 20 ng of DNA:

5 ng: 1 uL DNA (5 ng/uL) + 19 ul buffer

15 ng: 3 uL DNA (5 ng/uL) + 17 uL buffer

50 ng: 10 uL DNA (5 ng/uL) + 10 uL buffer

Comments:

-lane 2 – an error was made when adding the DNA

-lanes 4-6: this product was very low concentration.

Other notes:

The ladder and loading buffer are in a box in the -20 freezer door. Please use opened supplies first. You can also aliquot 18 uL of 0.1X loading buffer into 8-strip tubes using a repeater pipette.

Reordering Information

Sterivex DNA extraction

From CTV lab (modified by RMK 5/20/2026)

Personal RMK notes in RMK lab notebook, 3/21-10/25; 6/25/25

Overview:

This protocol was developed by the C Vesbach lab (University of New Mexico) for extracting DNA from lake water samples filtered on sterivex filters. Samples are prepared in the field and typically preserved by adding SLB (sucrose lysis buffer).

This protocol can be adjusted depending on what type and how much of sample you are using. This protocol will outline a sample that is from a sterivex filter, but can be imagined as a soil sample that is 0.2g (which is pretty dang small for a soil sample, so be aware that you'll have to scale up quite a bit). In this example, a filter was preserved in 200uL of SLB.

Another thing to consider is the volume of liquid sample substrate, and what type of vessel you are using. For instance, if you use a 2mL tube and want 1mL of sample at the phenol-chloroform (PC) step, you will have a very full tube, since you need equal volume of PC! However, if you are using a larger tube (i.e. 15mL tube), then you can use more material. Just think about how much you need at each step.

This is a 2-day process, with Day 1 being more intensive. There are optional stopping points as well.

Sample container: sterivex filter

top – has a red Luer lock cap

bottom – has a P10 tip that has been melted

Day One

1. Add equal volumes of 1% CTAB. (If you used 200uL SLB, then you will use 200uL of CTAB)
 - Add equal volume of SLB, if it wasn't added to the filter in the field
 - Cell lysis: CTAB disrupts the cell membranes by solubilizing lipids and denaturing proteins. This helps to release cellular components, including DNA, into the extraction buffer.
 - Binding of proteins: CTAB binds to proteins and removes them from the DNA solution. This is important because proteins can interfere with downstream applications such as PCR by inhibiting DNA polymerase activity.
 - DNA solubilization: CTAB helps to solubilize DNA by forming complexes with DNA molecules. These complexes are stable in the extraction buffer and can be separated from other cellular components.
 - Removal of contaminants: CTAB can help remove contaminants such as polysaccharides and phenolic compounds that may co-precipitate with DNA during the extraction process.
 - Inhibition of nucleases: CTAB can inhibit the activity of nucleases, enzymes that degrade DNA. This helps to preserve the integrity of the extracted DNA.
2. Add 2μL of proteinase K and 2μL of lysozyme
3. Seal both ends with tape. Incubate at 37°C for 30 minutes.
 - 37°C was the determined optimal temperature for the enzymes
 - Put on a rotating platform, a shaker, or occasionally flip the tubes to mix well
4. Remove from incubator and add 80μL of 10% SDS
5. Incubate again at 55°C for 30 minutes on the rotator.
6. Sterivex specific: Pull out lysate with a 1 ml luer-lock syringe that attaches to the luer lock and add to 2ml epitubes
 - Aim for ~500 to 400μL, try to be consistent
 - Return remaining filter to storage bag & store for future extractions
 - THIS CAN BE A STOPPING POINT -> store at -20C
7. Add equal volume (400 uL) of phenol:chloroform:isoamyl alcohol (p:ch:IAA). Invert 5 times.
 - Pull from below the upper phase; puppette up/down 1x before drawing up the solvent
 - Pro tip: take a clean new kim wipe, wrap it around the top of the tube, and then do your inversions. When you remove the kim wipe, is it still dry? If it is wet, you have a leak in your tube!
 - P:ch:IAA is hydrophobic, and will take proteins and other inhibitors up in solution. Your DNA, which has a charged sugar backbone, will stay

dissolved in the aqueous layer. <https://bitesizebio.com/3651/practical-application-of-phenol-chloroform-extraction/>

8. Spin for 5 minutes on a benchtop centrifuge at max speed
 - Room temp is okay. If using the nicer centrifuge, you can do 11,000 rcf as your speed.
 - This step is mostly about separating the phenol chloroform and your aqueous layer.
9. Carefully remove from centrifuge so you don't rattle the layers. Draw off aqueous layer into new tubes.
 - The top layer is the aqueous layer, and the bottom has the p:ch:IAA
 - Try not to pick up any of the white floaties that are at the interface between layers. If I started with 450µL of sample, I might take up 440µL of aqueous layer.
 - In *rare* cases related to pH, you may have an inversion of the phenol chloroform and aqueous layers, where the PC is on top instead of on bottom. This will quickly become evident in the next step, if there is no separation between layers when you add chloroform, as it will readily homogenize. So do not throw away tubes with the "bottom" layer until you are sure you have drawn off the aqueous layer.
10. Add equal volume (400 uL) of pure molecular grade chloroform (chloroform). Invert 5 times.
11. Spin for 5 minutes. Draw off aqueous layer into new tubes. THIS CAN BE A STOPPING POINT.
12. Add 0.1 volume (35 uL) of NaOAc and 2 volume (700 uL) of 95% EtOH. Invert 5 times.
13. Precipitate overnight in the freezer (-20°C).

Day Two

14. Using a refrigerated centrifuge, spin at 14000 rpm at 4°C for 45 minutes. Keep the hinge of the tubes pointed outwards, so that you know the DNA will pellet on the hinge-side of the tube.
15. Carefully, pour off the supernatant and add 1ml of 70% EtOH. Do not disturb pellet.
 - You may see a pellet on the hinge-side of the tube. If not, do not fear, believe in yourself, and keep going.
16. Using a refrigerated centrifuge, spin at 14000 rpm at 4°C for 30 minutes.
17. Carefully, pour off supernatant. Use a peppette to remove excess liquid if needed. Do not disturb the pellet.

18. Dry the tube without over-drying the pellet. If you have a speed vac, you may use this. If not, you can put tubes with lids open into an incubator.

- Check regularly to ensure they do not over-dry. Flick the back side of the tube – if it splatters into small droplets, it is still wet and needs to keep drying. If it is more slimy and boogery movement, that is your DNA pellet!
- Inspect whether the surface liquid remains. Do not overdry your pellet, it will be difficult to rehydrate & may denature
- If needed speed vac for 5 mins at room temperature (check every minute and remove tubes that have a “gel-like” pellet with no visible liquid

19. Resuspend in 40 μ L of 10mM Tris.

- Pipette up and down a couple times to ensure it is fully suspended. You can *lightly* tap on a vortex, and then spin down on a small benchtop centrifuge.
- Ensure that the final resting tube is labeled very clearly

20. Freeze until ready to use

- Before freezing, you may choose to nanodrop to see if you have any DNA. Doing this before freezing prevents additional freeze-thaw.

Large volume DNA extraction (ALPS)

From CTV lab (modified by RMK 5/20/2026)

Personal RMK notes in RMK lab notebook, 3/21-10/25; 7/16/25

This protocol will outline a sample that is from a 50mL conical tube with 3mL of SLB preserving a filter, as with ALPS. The concentrations of some reagents are not exactly adjusted to scale of the Limno Sterivex protocol, but have been refined to work regardless while not over-using reagents. Lots of excess sample will remain for long-term storage, and can be extracted again successfully at a later date.

This is a 2-day process, with Day 1 being more intensive. There are optional stopping points as well. This protocol will split samples into two tubes, so you will have double the number of samples after step 6.

Day One

(note: 24 samples takes 1 person ~6 hrs)

21. Thaw samples on ice (47 mm GFF filters in 3 mL of SLB)

22. Add equal volumes (3 mL) of 1% CTAB. (ALPS uses 3mL SLB, so you will add 3mL of CTAB)

- Cell lysis: CTAB disrupts the cell membranes by solubilizing lipids and denaturing proteins. This helps to release cellular components, including DNA, into the extraction buffer.
- Binding of proteins: CTAB binds to proteins and removes them from the DNA solution. This is important because proteins can interfere with downstream applications such as PCR by inhibiting DNA polymerase activity.
- DNA solubilization: CTAB helps to solubilize DNA by forming complexes with DNA molecules. These complexes are stable in the extraction buffer and can be separated from other cellular components.
- Removal of contaminants: CTAB can help remove contaminants such as polysaccharides and phenolic compounds that may co-precipitate with DNA during the extraction process.
- Inhibition of nucleases: CTAB can inhibit the activity of nucleases, enzymes that degrade DNA. This helps to preserve the integrity of the extracted DNA.

23. Add 10 μ L of proteinase K and 10 μ L of lysozyme.

24. Incubate at 37°C for 30 minutes. (use the large shaking incubator in the teaching lab)

- Make sure filter is immersed in the buffer
 - 37°C was the determined optimal temperature for the enzymes
 - Put on a rotating platform, a shaker, or occasionally flip the tubes to mix well
 - Invert by hand every 10 mins
25. Remove from incubator and add 1mL of 10% SDS (use a 25 mL tip with the repeater pipette)
26. Incubate at 37°C for 30 minutes.
- 37°C was the determined optimal temperature for the enzymes
 - Put on a rotating platform, a shaker, or occasionally flip the tubes to mix well
27. Large volume specific: From each sample, add two splits of 500 μ L of aqueous solution into two new 2mL tubes.
- You may label A and B, but they will eventually be combined again, so it doesn't matter so much
 - Store excess sample at -80°C
 - THIS CAN BE A STOPPING POINT
28. Add equal volume (500 μ L) of phenol:chloroform:isoamyl alcohol (p:ch:IAA), in this case 500 μ L. Invert 5 times.
- Pull from below the upper phase; puppette up/down 1x before drawing up the solvent
 - Pro tip: take a clean new kim wipe, wrap it around the top of the tube, and then do your inversions. When you remove the kim wipe, is it still dry? If it is wet, you have a leak in your tube!
 - P:ch:IAA is hydrophobic, and will take proteins and other inhibitors up in solution. Your DNA, which has a charged sugar backbone, will stay dissolved in the aqueous layer. <https://bitesizebio.com/3651/practical-application-of-phenol-chloroform-extraction/>
29. Spin for 5 minutes on a benchtop centrifuge at max speed
- Room temp is okay. If using the nicer centrifuge, you can do 11,000 rcf as your speed.
 - This step is mostly about separating the phenol chloroform and your aqueous layer.
30. Carefully remove from centrifuge so you don't rattle the layers. Draw off aqueous layer into new tubes.
- The top layer is the aqueous layer, and the bottom has the p:ch:IAA
 - Try not to pick up any of the white floaties that are at the interface between layers. If I started with 500 μ L of sample, I might take up 490 μ L of aqueous layer.
 - If interface is not very distinct, you can add another 500 μ L of p:ch:IAA and spin again

- In *rare* cases related to pH, you may have an inversion of the phenol chloroform and aqueous layers, where the PC is on top instead of on bottom. This will quickly become evident in the next step, if there is no separation between layers when you add chloroform, as it will readily homogenize. So do not throw away tubes with the “bottom” layer until you are sure you have drawn off the aqueous layer.
31. Add equal volume (500 μ L) of pure molecular grade chloroform (chloroform). Invert 5 times.
 32. Spin for 5 minutes. Draw off aqueous layer into new tubes. THIS CAN BE A STOPPING POINT.
 - Try not to pick up any of the chloroform, as this will interfere with downstream PCR. If I started with 490 μ L of sample, I might take up 480 μ L of aqueous layer.
 33. Add 0.1 volume of NaOAc ($480 \times 0.1 = 48 \mu$ L) and 2 volume of 95% EtOH ($480 \times 2 = 960 \mu$ L). Invert 5 times.
 34. Precipitate overnight in the freezer (-20°C).
-

Day Two

1. Using a refrigerated centrifuge, spin at 14000 rpm at 4°C for 45 minutes. Keep the hinge of the tubes pointed outwards, so that you know the DNA will pellet on the hinge-side of the tube.
2. Carefully, pour off the supernatant and add 1 ml of 70% EtOH (no mixing).
 - You may see a pellet on the hinge-side of the tube. If not, do not fear, believe in yourself, and keep going.
3. Using a refrigerated centrifuge, spin at 14000 rpm at 4°C for 30 minutes.
4. Carefully, pour off supernatant. Use a P200 to carefully draw off any remaining liquid, avoiding the pellet
5. Dry the tube without over-drying the pellet. If you have a speed vac, you may use this. If not, you can put tubes with lids open into an incubator.
 - Check regularly to ensure they do not over-dry. Flick the back side of the tube – if it splatters into small droplets, it is still wet and needs to keep drying. If it is more slimy and boogery movement, that is your DNA pellet!
6. Resuspend ONE of the two splits with 40 μ L of 10mM Tris.
 - Pipette up and down a several times to ensure it is *fully* suspended. You can *lightly* tap on a vortex, and then spin down on a small benchtop centrifuge.
7. Remove the 40 μ L of 10mM Tris from the first split and add this resuspended DNA into the second split

- Pipette up and down to fully resuspend. The final result should be one tube per sample with 40 μ L Tris, NOT two tubes per sample, or 40+40 μ L Tris.
 - Ensure that the final resting tube is labeled very clearly
8. Freeze until ready to use
- Before freezing, you may choose to nanodrop to see if you have any DNA. Doing this before freezing prevents additional freeze-thaw.

Buffers & solutions for sterivex & large format DNA

SLB

pH 9.0

20mM EDTA, 400 mM NaCl, 0.7M sucrose, and 50 mM Tris

For 1 liter:

- combine in a beaker with a stir bar
 - o 40mL of 0.5M EDTA
 - o 8mL 5M NaCl
 - o 50mL 1M Tris (pH 9)
- add ~800 mL DI water
- slowly add 239.61g sucrose (ultra pure from VWR, DNase RNase free), stir until dissolved
- **filter sterilize (do not autoclave, or you'll get a giant jolly rancher)**

1% Cetyl Trimethyl Ammonium Bromide (CTAB)

- Add 100 mL of RO H₂O into a beaker with a stir bar.
- Add:
 - 2 g of CTAB
 - 30 mL of 5 M NaCl
 - 4 mL of .5 M EDTA
- Stir till it dissolves, though more water may need to be added
- Bring volume up to 200 mL with RO H₂O
- **Filter Sterilize**

Lysozyme (200 µg/µl)

- Add 5 mL of F.S.DI H₂O to 1 g lysozyme. Mix well
- Aliquot small amounts into Epi Tubes (50 µL aliquots is good)
- Freeze the aliquots

Proteinase K (20 µg/µl)

- Add 5 ml of F.S.DI water to the Proteinase K (PK) bottle containing 100 mg of PK.
- Mix well and Aliquot small amounts into Epi tubes
- Freeze the aliquots

10% SDS

It is best to work in a fume hood/wear a mask. Make sure to clean up after working with SDS.

- Add 10 g of SDS to 90 mL of DI water. Heat and stir <68 °C.
- Adjust pH to 7.2 once the SDS is fully dissolved.
- Adjust the volume to 100 mL.
- **Filter sterilize.**

Phenol Chloroform:Isoamyl Alcohol

Ratio by Volume: 25:24:1

- Add phenol, Chloroform, and IsoamylAlcohol in the above ratio in a **glass graduated cylinder**.
- Add equal amounts of TE in a **capped glass container**. Shake the solution for several minutes, until no separation is observed. Leave for a day in the fridge (4 °C).
- Draw off the TE, the top layer, and put in the same amount of fresh TE in.
- Shake again until no separation is observed and leave for a day in the fridge (4 °C).
- Draw off TE and put equal amounts of unused TE in and shake for several minutes until no separation is observed. Store in 4 °C in the fridge.

3 M NaOAc (Sodium Acetate)

pH 5.2

Use the Hydrate form (MW=136.08)

- Dissolve 40.81 g of NaOAc into ~60 mL of DI water.
 - If using anhydrous form, add 24.61 g into ~60 mL of DI water.
- Adjust pH to 5.2 with Glacial Acetic Acid.
- Bring the final volume to 100 mL
- Filter sterilize or autoclave.

10 mM Tris, pH8

Recipe for 100 mL

Component	Amount
Tris base	0.121 g
Molecular-grade water	Bring to 100 mL final volume
HCl	Add dropwise to pH 8.0

Recipe for 1 L

Component	Amount
Tris base	1.211 g
Molecular-grade water	Bring to 1 L final volume
HCl	Add dropwise to pH 8.0

Notes:

Filter sterilize

Do not use TE buffer, EDTA can inhibit some downstream reactions

Extraction of mat samples (T. Mackey lab)

See Appendix 4

Nextera sequencing protocol

Summary of Nextera Sequencing Protocol

Overview & Notes:

1. Inform CBFG (Andor Kiss) 1-week ahead regarding your sequence plans. He may need to dilute primers, or perform instrument maintenance.
2. Use the “molecular” pipettes; be sure to UV treat the day before
3. Check whether electronic pipettors are charged
4. This protocol is specific for 18S primers, but you can adjust conditions of PCR#1 and use for any primers with Nextera adaptors

Step	Approximate Time	CBFG Reservation Needed
1. Create Master Sample Sheet(s)	1 hr	No
2. Aliquot template DNA into 96-well plates	1 hr/plate	No
3. Prepare/perform PCR #1	3 hrs/plate	No
4. Spot check PCR #1 on Egel	0.5 hrs/plate	No
5. Dilute PCR #1	10 mins	No
6. Perform PCR #2	12 mins/plate	Yes-robot
7. Spot check PCR #1 on Egel	0.5 hrs/plate	No
8. Normalization/PCR Cleanup	0.5 hrs/plate + ON Incubation	No
9. Pool PCRs	35 mins/plate	Yes-robot
10. Quantify Libraries	2 hrs	Yes-BioRad CFX
11. Combine Libraries	10 min	No
12. Quantify Pooled Library	2 hrs	Yes-BioRad CFX
13. Load Sequence Cartridge	3 hrs	Yes-MiSeq
14. Run MiSeq	2 days	Yes-MiSeq

Typical Weekly Set-up (if you have 1 96-well plate – if you have >1 plate, you will need to expand):

Day 1: Prepare the Master Sample Sheet; aliquot out the template DNA

Day 2: Perform PCR #1 (Note, you can run 3 PCR plates simultaneously on the Thermocyclers in the RMK lab). Spot check on Egel.

Day 3: Dilute PCR #1. Perform PCR#2. Spot check on Egel. Start Normalization/PCR Clean-up.

Day 4: Finish Normalization. Pool Samples. Quantify Libraries. Pool Libraries.

Day 5: Quantify pooled Library. Run MiSeq.

Detailed Protocol (updated by RMK 05/20/2026)

I: SET-UP MASTER DNA PLATE(S)

1. Create a Master Sample Sheet to track DNA template samples. See example of best practices below. Use a separate excel sheet for each 96-well plate

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Well	sampl	renamed	character	conc.	dil	new conc	sample ty	project name	
2	A1	ADA B1	ADAB1_m	7	160.76	1:25	6.4	2324_LZ	2324_LZ	
3										

..\MCM6\MCM6 Amplicon Sequencing\Sample Planning Sheet_Blank.xlsx

2. Set up genomic DNA plate (1 uL template per well)
 - a. Print a copy of all of master sample sheets
 - b. Samples may need to be diluted 1:10 or 1:25
 - c. Preferably work with a buddy: one person hands over the sample tube, calls out the correct well & checks off the sample; second person pipettes sample into correct well
 - d. If you anticipate sequencing the DNA template >once, consider making a “master DNA template” plate with >1 uL.

II: Run PCR #1/ Spot Check/ Dilute

3. 1st rxn PCR
 - a. Primers: target-specific primers with Nextera Adapters
 - b. Set up a master mix (below is for 1x96 well plate, VWR #83007-374)

Component	1x	110x
Gotaq Hotstart Mix	12.5ul	1375ul
F Primer (100uM)	0.1ul	11ul
R Primer (100uM)	0.1ul	11ul
Water	11.3ul	1243ul
Template	1ul	/
Total	25ul	/

- c. Mix gotaq, primers, water and add 24ul to each well with gDNA; Rainin P1000 multichannel pipette on repeater function works well

4. Seal plate with the heat seal (Azenta #4T1-0541):
 - a. Turn on Thermo Heat Sealer at least 10 mins before use; pre-heat light will stop blinking when it has reached temp
 - b. Place heat seal frosted side down
 - c. Place plate and seal in heat sealer
 - d. Pull down lever and hold until timer beeps after 3 sec. Be sure to pull lever slowly so that seal doesn't get displaced, and then put some pressure on the handle when it comes in contact with the plate.
 - e. Check that seal is evenly sealed on wells; repeat if needed
 - f. Turn off sealer after use.

5. , mix, run PCR protocol
 - a. Adapted PCR conditions, depending on your primers.
 - b. 18S (primers: Euk_BR_Nextera/Euk-1391r_Nextera (primer sequences from CTV; Note: we added "nextera suffix b/c the EMP primers have same name)
 - i. 94C 3min
 - ii. 94C 45sec
 - iii. 57C 60sec
 - iv. 72C 90sec
 - v. Repeat step step ii-iv 29x (30x total)
 - vi. 72C 10min
 - vii. 4C hold

6. Spot check 10 samples per plate on the Invitrogen egel.
 - a. Expected sizes: 18S – 260 bp
7. Dilute PCR #1 products 1:10 in DNA-grade water (eg: 5 uL template + 45 uL water)
8. Transfer 3 uL to fresh plate -> this is your template for PCR #2.

III: Run PCR #2

9. 2nd rxn PCR

- a. Prepare a master mix of GoTaq & water. 1-4 x 96-well plates can be run on the liquid handling robot. The calculations below are for 1 plate.
- b. Primers for PCR#2 are universal for any template with Nextera adapters. CBFG keeps these primers in their -20 freezer in main CBFG lab.

Component	1x	110x
Gotaq Hotstart Mix	12.5ul	1375ul
F Primer (10uM)	1ul	/
R Primer (10uM)	1ul	/
Water	7.5ul	825ul
Template	3ul	/
Total	25ul	/

10. Run Robot Nextera PCR3#2 Robot Protocol

Robot Instructions:

- a. Turn on robot & computer; turn on the Hepa filter
- b. Load protocol: Nextera-V2-2PCRSetup_CBFG (protocol time: 12 mins)
- c. Check volumetrics: reaction: 20 uL; total volume: 2200 ul (for 1 plate); adjust total volume as needed
- d. Refer to diagram on program for placement of materials:
 - i. Thermo adaptor+1 template plate (in position TMX)
 - ii. Thermo adaptor+1 primer plate with double-barcoded nextera primers (from CBFG) (in A2 position)
 - iii. Eppendorf tip hold+2 boxes of P50 tips (in B1 and B2 position)
 - iv. 1 x 30 mL reservoir** containing master mix in position 4 (of the C2 position) **can recycle reservoirs for future runs
 - v. Garbage bag (50X autoclave bag): must be placed so that there are no wrinkles & secured with provided metal fasteners. Put two fasteners on grabber side of garbage & 1 on the right side-bend in the outside of the fasteners in a little to ensure nothing will snag on them.

- e. Start run: follow thru prompts; choose: “used required minimum volumes”, “automatic tool selection”, “96” samples.
 - f. Note: if you have multiple plates of template to sequence, make up enough master mix for all plates (remember to adjust the final vol. in the program); replace template/primers/tips between runs & restart protocol
 - g. When you are finished, do a UV treatment: you will need to remove all hardware from the machine (there will be a warning reminding you)
 - h. UV treatment takes 15 min -> return to replace all hardware in the robot
 - i. Switch off robot and computer
 - j. Fill out materials used in the CBFGB binder, including primers.
11. Seal Plate with thermal seal (described above), mix, run PCR #2
- a. 18S (22 mi duration)
 - i. 94C 3min
 - ii. 94C 30sec
 - iii. 55C 30sec
 - iv. 72C 30sec
 - v. Repeat ii-iv 8x (9x total)
 - vi. 72C 5min
 - vii. 4C hold
12. Spot check 2-3 samples per plate on the Invitrogen egel. Load 1-2 samples from PCR#1: PCR#2 produced should be ~50 bp larger

Clean/normalize amplicons, pool amplicons

13. Clean/normalize libraries with Just-a-Plate 96-well PCR normalization & purification kit (Charm Biotech #JN-120-10).
 - a. Follow Kit Directions
 - b. Rainin P200 multichannel is good for transfers between plates
 - c. Eppendorf P300 manual multichannel is good for buffer transfers & mixing
 - d. Follow manufacturer's instructions
 - e. Elute in 20 uL
 - f. Transfer entire volume to fresh plate (VWR) prior to proceeding to pooling library.

14. Pool Libraries on robot (protocol: EMPAmpSeqPoolIII – run time: 35 mins)
 - a. 96-well plate(s) of normalized/cleaned samples+thermoadapter (in TMX2)
 - b. Eppendorf tip holder + 1 rack of P50 tips
 - c. 1 low-bind (DNA LoBind Fisher# 13-698-791) 1.5 mL tube (in position 1 of the tube adapter): check that the tube is fitting snugly in slot so it can't catch on anything
 - d. Garbage bag
 - e. Repeat process, if you have multiple libraries to pool
 - f. Follow general start-up and shut-down procedures for the robot as described above.

Quantify libraries, pool libraries

15. Library quantitation (Kapa or NEBNext #E7630S/L)
 - a. Generally follow manufacturer instructions.
 - b. Library dilutions that RMK lab typically does:
 - i. 1:100 5 uL library + 495 uL 1X dilution buffer ->briefly vortex
 - ii. 1:1000 10 uL of 1:100 lib + 90 uL 1X dilution buffer ->briefly vortex
 - iii. 1:5000 10 uL of 1:1000 lib + 40 uL 1X dilution buffer ->briefly vortex
 - iv. 1:10000 10 uL of 1:5000 lib + 10 uL 1X dilution buffer
 - c. Prepare dilutions for each library
 - d. NTC should be 4 uL 1x dilution buffer for template
 - e. General rx: 4 uL template + 16 uL of master mix
 - f. Transfer reactions to a qPCR plate. Typical layout:

Std 1	Std 1	Std 1	Std 2	Std 2	Std 2	Std 3	Std 3	Std 3	Std 4	Std 4	Std 4
Std 5	Std 5	Std 5	Std 6	Std 6	Std 6	NTC	NTC	NTC			
1:1K	1:1K	1:1K	1:5K	1:5K	1:5K	1:10K	1:10K	1:10K			

- g. NEB website for library quantification:
<https://nebiocalculator.neb.com/#!/qPCRlibQnt>

16. If you have >1 library, pool libraries. Repeat quantification on pooled library, preferably the morning of the MiSeq Run.
 Illumina pooling calculator:
<https://support.illumina.com/help/pooling-calculator/pooling-calculator.htm>

17. If concentration is too low, concentrate sample in the Speed Vac (see separate protocol)

Prepare sample sheet, library, load cartridge, run MiSeq

18. Prepare sample sheet for MiSeq instrument. Below is a link to the sample sheet needed for samples with the Nextera barcodes
 - a. https://drive.google.com/open?id=1mZQ5ZF8OWnNMdYzrhbZfg2ugJk5xJehM&usp=drive_fs
19. Set up Miseq run
 - a. Follow the CBFQ SOP for MiSeq (Appendix 3)
 - b. Dilute library and phix and NaOH according to CBFQ protocols
 - c. Will want to create a spreadsheet for the miseq beforehand – can ask Andor how to do this – it’s super easy and can be done on the MiSeq machine
 - d. Once you get to your 600ul of solution to be loaded (90% lib + 10% PhiX), you load this into the well on the cartridge that says “Load Sample” and that is all you need to do (everything else needed is already in the cartridge, so prepping the cartridge is super easy and only need to load the sample)
 - e. Start the run as normal

CBFG MiSeq Amplicon SOP

The CBFG MiSeq Amplicon SOP is the authoritative protocol for EMP-style amplicon sequencing, MiSeq loading, run setup, and demultiplexing. RMK Lab students should use the RMK protocol book for project-specific planning, sample tracking, and lab preparation, but should consult the annotated CBFG SOP before performing CBFG instrument-dependent steps, especially robot setup, library quantification, MiSeq cartridge preparation, sample sheet creation, and run initiation (Appendix 3).

Speed Vac

A SpeedVac is used to gently and safely remove solvents from biological and chemical samples. It combines vacuum pressure, centrifugal force, and controlled heat to rapidly evaporate liquids without damaging or losing delicate samples (like DNA, proteins, or synthesized compounds).

Protocol:

1. Sign-up for the Speed Vac is through CBFQ (calcium)
2. Turn on the power: turn on backup power unit & speed vac 30 mins before use.
3. Program: load a program or program in time & temp
 - a. For DNA concentration – Program #9: 4°C, 120 mins
 - b. DNA sample: parafilm the top of an open epitube; poke a few holes in the top with a P10 tip
 - c. Will reduce from ~1 mL to 100 uL
4. Load your samples
5. Start run -> listen for the pump to engage, atm will increase on gage
6. End run -> at end of run, atm will return to zero & lock will disengage
 - a. If there is a malfunction and atm does not decrease, can use a bleed valve on vacuum to relieve pressure

Liquid Handing Robot

The CBFG protocol uses the **Eppendorf epMotion 5073m NGS liquid-handling workstation**. The CBFG MiSeq amplicon SOP notes that the sequencing protocols have been adapted for **96-well microplates**, and that while other plastics/labware can technically be used, new labware requires substantial troubleshooting; therefore, students should use the tested/recommended labware unless there is a compelling reason not to. Reservation of the robot is through the CBFG booking system (Calcium)

The robot is used for several programmed sequencing-library steps, including:

Workflow	Robot use	Program/protocol name	Approx. time
EMP/CBFG amplicon protocol	Initial amplicon PCR setup	EMP Amplicon Protocol I–III	not listed
EMP/CBFG amplicon protocol	Recombine triplicate PCR plates	EMP Amp Post-PCR	not listed
Nextera protocol	PCR #2 setup	Nextera-V2-2PCRSetup_CBFG	~12 min/plate
Both protocols	Pool cleaned/normalized libraries	EMPampSeqPoolIII	~35 min/plate

Common robot start-up/shut-down notes

Start-up

1. Turn on the robot,
2. Turn on the computer: log in with computer using login ID; click on “epMotion app”; check top right corner for green check mark
3. Turn on the HEPA filter: click on settings>devices>clean CAP>turn on HEPA filter
4. Load the appropriate protocol: >Application Editor
5. Check/confirm volumetrics before starting the run.
6. Confirm deck layout using the diagram in the robot program.
7. Confirm garbage bag placement and tip availability.
8. Start the run and follow prompts.

Shut-down / cleanup

After robot use:

1. Remove all hardware before UV treatment.
2. Run UV treatment for **15 minutes**.
3. Replace hardware after UV treatment.
4. Switch off the robot and computer.

Garbage bag setup

The garbage bag needs special attention:

- Use a **50× autoclave bag**.
- Place it so there are **no wrinkles**.
- Secure it with the provided metal fasteners.
- Place **two fasteners on the grabber side** of the garbage bag.
- Place **one fastener on the right side**.
- Bend the outside of the fasteners inward slightly so nothing snags on them.

Multiple-plate note

For multiple template plates:

- Make enough master mix for all plates.
- Adjust the final volume in the robot program.
- Replace the template plate, primer plate, and tips between runs.
- Restart the protocol for each plate.

Nextera PCR #2 setup

Purpose

Use the liquid-handling robot to set up PCR #2 for Nextera-style amplicon sequencing. This step adds the universal Nextera indexing primers to PCR #1 products that already contain Nextera adapter tails. PCR #2 F and R primers are universal for any template with Nextera adapters: CBFG keeps these primers in the small -80°C freezer in the robot room.

Timing and capacity

1–4 × 96-well plates can be run on the liquid-handling robot. The robot protocol Nextera-V2-2PCRSetup_CBFG takes approximately **12 minutes per plate**.

PCR #2 master mix

For one 96-well plate, prepare enough GoTaq/water master mix for 110 reactions:

Component	1 reaction	110 reactions
GoTaq HotStart Mix	12.5 µL	1375 µL
Water	7.5 µL	825 µL
F primer, 10 µM	1 µL	added from primer plate
R primer, 10 µM	1 µL	added from primer plate
Template	3 µL	from template plate

Component	1 reaction	110 reactions
Total	25 μ L	—

Program

Load robot protocol:

Nextera-V2-2PCRSetsup_CBFG

Protocol time: ~**12 minutes**

Check volumetrics before running:

Setting	Value
Reaction volume	20 μ L
Total volume for 1 plate	2200 μ L

Deck layout for Nextera PCR #2

Robot deck item	Location
Thermoadaptor + template plate	TMX
Thermoadaptor + primer plate with double-barcoded Nextera primers	A2
Eppendorf tip holder + 2 boxes P50 tips	B1 and B2
Reservoir* containing master mix	position 4 of C2
Garbage bag, 50 \times autoclave bag	robot waste position

*Reservoirs can be recycled for future runs.

Pooling normalized/cleaned libraries

Purpose

Use the robot to pool cleaned/normalized amplicon libraries (i.e. following Just-a-Plate cleanup/normalization step) into a single low-bind tube before qPCR quantification.

Program

Load robot protocol:

EMPAmSeqPoolIII

Run time: ~35 minutes

Required materials and deck setup

Robot deck item	Location / note
96-well plate(s) of normalized/cleaned samples + thermoadaptor	TMX2
Eppendorf tip holder + 1 rack P50 tips	robot deck
1.5 mL DNA LoBind tube*	position 1 of tube adapter
Garbage bag	robot waste position

*check that the 1.5 mL LoBind tube is sitting **snugly** in the tube-adapter slot so it cannot catch on anything during the run.

For multiple libraries, repeat the pooling process for each library and follow the same start-up/shut-down procedures used for the PCR #2 robot setup.

Robot notes from EMP/CBFG MiSeq amplicon protocol

The CBFG MiSeq amplicon protocol uses the robot more extensively for the EMP-style amplicon workflow. (also see CBFG MiSeq Amplicon SOP, Appendix 3)

The SOP lists the most relevant pre-programmed epMotion protocols in likely use order. Protocols are located in “Application Editor: EMP Protocols”

- 1. EMP Amplicon Protocol I–III**
Used for amplicon PCR setup; the differences among I–III are in the PCR plates.
- 2. EMP Amp Post-PCR Protocol**
Used after PCR to recombine three 25 μ L PCR plates into one 75 μ L plate.
- 3. EMP Amp SeqPool III (described above)**
Used to pool normalized amplicons into a 1.5 mL LoBind tube.

EMP amplicon PCR setup notes

For the EMP workflow, the robot combines:

- gDNA plate
- EMP reverse primer plate (from CBFG)
- forward primer
- GoTaq G2 Hot Start Master Mix
- ddH₂O

MasterMix:

Component	Per Rxn (µL)	Per 110 Rxns (µL)
GoTaq® G2 Hot Start Colorless Master Mix	37.50	4,125.00
FOR emp (515f) Primer (100 µM)	0.15	16.50
ddH ₂ O	31.35	3,448.50
Total Volume	69.00	7590 (÷ 4 = 1898 per 2 mL tube)

Additional notes from RP on EMP protocols:

- Place master mix reservoir in slot 4 of C2 metal holder
- Don't forget to transfer Just-a-Plate contents to fresh 96-well plate (always VWR)
- For pooling, use 10 uL for pool
- LoBind tube in slot 1 of metal holder C2 (sometimes in fridge)

Appendix 1: General Lab Supplies

Before beginning any protocol, confirm that all required reagents, plastics, equipment reservations, sample sheets, and plate maps are ready. Do not begin a sequencing workflow unless the sample sheet has been checked, the plate map has been printed, controls have been included, and the required CBFGE equipment has been reserved. For rare or irreplaceable samples, confirm the plan with RMK or the project lead before thawing samples.

These supplies are used across DNA extraction, PCR setup, library preparation, and sequencing workflows.

Item	Use/Notes
Nitrile gloves	Change frequently, especially between sample handling, PCR setup, and post-PCR work.
Lab coats	Required for wet lab work.
Kimwipes	Used for general cleanup and for checking tube leaks during phenol-chloroform inversions.
Ice buckets	Used for thawing samples and keeping reagents cold.
Tube racks	For 1.5 mL, 2 mL, 15 mL, and 50 mL tubes.
1.5 mL microcentrifuge tubes	General sample handling; DNA LoBind tubes preferred for final DNA or libraries.
2 mL microcentrifuge tubes	Used during phenol-chloroform extraction and precipitation steps.
15 mL conical tubes	Useful for larger-volume reagent prep or extraction handling.
50 mL conical tubes	Used for large-volume sample storage and extraction workflows.
Parafilm	Used in SpeedVac workflow for partially covering open tubes.
Autoclave bags	Required for liquid-handling robot garbage bag setup; robot protocol specifies 50× autoclave bags.
Molecular-grade water / nuclease-free water	Used for PCR, dilutions, and library preparation.
Bleach / ethanol / DNA decontamination solution	For workspace cleaning before PCR setup and sample handling.

Pipettes and Tips

Item	Use/Notes
Molecular pipettes	Dedicated pipettes for PCR/library prep; UV-treat before sequencing workflows.
Rainin electronic pipettes	Used for repetitive pipetting and plate setup; check charge before use.
Rainin multichannel pipettes	Useful for 96-well plate work, PCR setup, cleanup, and transfers.
Rainin P1000 multichannel pipette	Nextera protocol notes this works well on repeater function for adding PCR #1 master mix to plates.
Rainin P200 multichannel pipette	Useful for transfers during cleanup/normalization.
P10, P20, P200, P1000 single-channel pipettes	General liquid handling.
Filter tips, 10 μ L XL	Required for PCR and DNA work. Supplies list includes USA Scientific 1120-3710.
Filter tips, 200 μ L	Required for PCR and DNA work. Supplies list includes USA Scientific 1120-8710 and Rainin-compatible BIOTIX tips.
Filter tips, 1000 μ L	Required for extraction and sequencing workflows. Supplies list includes USA Scientific 1126-7710 and Rainin-compatible BIOTIX tips.
Eppendorf P50 robot tips	Used by the Eppendorf epMotion robot for Nextera PCR #2 setup and library pooling.

DNA Extraction Reagents

These are used primarily for Sterivex, large-volume filter, and phenol-chloroform DNA extraction protocols.

Reagent	Use/Notes
SLB, sucrose lysis buffer	Field preservation/sample lysis buffer; Sterivex samples are often preserved in SLB.
1% CTAB	Added at equal volume to SLB-preserved samples; used for cell lysis, protein binding, contaminant removal, and nuclease inhibition.
Proteinase K	Used during lysis; Sterivex protocol uses 2 μ L, large-volume protocol uses 10 μ L.
Lysozyme	Used during lysis; Sterivex protocol uses 2 μ L, large-volume protocol uses 10 μ L.
10% SDS	Added after initial enzyme incubation; Sterivex protocol uses 80 μ L, large-volume protocol uses 1 mL.
Phenol:chloroform:isoamyl alcohol	Used to separate DNA-containing aqueous layer from proteins and inhibitors; must be handled in fume hood.
Molecular-grade chloroform	Used after phenol-chloroform step to further clean the aqueous layer.
Sodium acetate, NaOAc	Added at 0.1 volume before ethanol precipitation.
95–100% ethanol	Used for DNA precipitation.
70% ethanol	Used to wash DNA pellet after precipitation.
10 mM Tris	Used to resuspend final DNA pellet; Sterivex protocol uses 40 μ L.

DNA Extraction Equipment

Equipment	Use/Notes
Fume hood	Required for phenol:chloroform:isoamyl alcohol and chloroform handling.
Benchtop centrifuge	Used for phase separation after phenol-chloroform/chloroform steps.
Refrigerated centrifuge	Used for DNA precipitation spins; protocols specify 14,000 rpm at 4°C for 45 minutes followed by a 70% ethanol wash spin.
Large shaking incubator	Used during large-volume DNA extraction incubations.
Rotator or rotating platform	Used during Sterivex and extraction incubations.
-20°C freezer	Used for overnight precipitation and stopping points.
-80°C freezer	Used for long-term storage of excess samples in large-volume protocol.
SpeedVac	Used to concentrate DNA or dry pellets carefully; CBFV SpeedVac is reserved through Calcium.
NanoDrop or equivalent spectrophotometer	Used to check DNA concentration/purity before freezing or sequencing prep.
Vortex mixer	Used carefully for resuspension and reagent mixing.
Mini benchtop centrifuge	Used for quick spin-downs after resuspension or mixing.

Sterivex-Specific Supplies

Item	Use/Notes
Sterivex filters	Field-filtered samples, often preserved with SLB.
Red Luer-lock caps	Used to seal Sterivex filter top.
Melted P10 tip plug	Used to seal the bottom of Sterivex filters.
Tape	Used to seal Sterivex ends during incubation.
1 mL sterile Luer-lock syringes	Used to pull lysate from Sterivex filter into 2 mL tubes.
Labeled storage bags	Used to return remaining Sterivex filters to storage after lysate removal.

Large-Volume Filter Extraction Supplies

Item	Use/Notes
47 mm GFF filters	Large-volume/ALPS-style samples.
50 mL conical tubes	Sample container for filters preserved in 3 mL SLB.
1% CTAB	Added at equal volume to SLB; ALPS-style samples use 3 mL CTAB with 3 mL SLB.
Repeater pipette and large-volume tips	Used for adding 10% SDS; large-volume protocol notes use of a 25 mL tip with repeater pipette.
2 mL tubes	Used to split lysate into paired A/B tubes before phenol-chloroform processing.

PCR and Amplicon Sequencing Supplies

Item	Use/Notes
96-well PCR plates	Nextera protocol uses VWR #83007-374; also listed in sequencing supplies.
96-well aluminum membrane sealing film	Listed in supplies list as VWR #470347-462.
96-well heat seals	Listed as Azenta #4T1-0541 / Fisher #NC2306755; Nextera protocol uses Azenta heat seals.
8-tube PCR strips	Listed in supplies as USA Scientific 1402-2900.
GoTaq G2 Hot Start Colorless Master Mix	Used for EMP and Nextera PCR reactions; listed in supplies as Promega M7433.
DNA-grade / nuclease-free water	Used in PCR master mixes and dilutions; supplies list includes Invitrogen nuclease-free water.
Target-specific primers with Nextera adapters	Used in Nextera PCR #1.
Universal Nextera PCR #2 primers	Used in Nextera PCR #2; stored by CBFG in the small -80°C freezer in the robot room.
EMP forward and reverse primers	Used for EMP/CBFG amplicon workflow.
DNA template plates	Used for 96-well sequencing workflows.
Master sample sheets / plate maps	Required for sample tracking; Nextera protocol recommends a separate Excel sheet for each 96-well plate.

PCR and Library Preparation Equipment

Equipment	Use/Notes
Thermocyclers	Used for PCR #1 and PCR #2; Nextera protocol notes that up to three PCR plates can be run simultaneously on RMK lab thermocyclers.
Thermo heat sealer	Used to seal 96-well PCR plates; should be turned on at least 10 minutes before use.
Invitrogen E-Gel system	Used to spot-check PCR products; Nextera protocol recommends checking 10 samples after PCR #1 and 2–3 samples after PCR #2.
Gel documentation system	Used if running agarose gels for PCR checks.
Eppendorf epMotion 5073m NGS liquid-handling workstation	Used for programmed sequencing-library steps, including EMP PCR setup, EMP post-PCR recombination, Nextera PCR #2 setup, and pooling cleaned/normalized libraries.
HEPA filter on robot	Turn on before robot use.
Robot thermoadaptors	Used for template plates, primer plates, and normalized library plates.
Robot reservoirs	Used for master mix during robot protocols.
Computer with epMotion software	Used to load robot protocols through Application Editor.

Library Cleanup, Normalization, and Pooling Supplies

Item	Use/Notes
Just-a-Plate 96-well PCR normalization and purification kit	Used for cleanup/normalization; supplies list gives Charm Biotech #JN-120-10.
Fresh VWR 96-well plates	Used after cleanup/normalization before pooling.
1.5 mL DNA LoBind tubes	Used for pooled libraries and dilutions; supplies list includes Eppendorf DNA LoBind tubes.
Robot pooling protocol	EMPAmpSeqPoolIII pools cleaned/normalized libraries into a LoBind tube; run time approximately 35 minutes.
SpeedVac	May be used to reduce pooled library volume if needed. CBFV SOP notes pooled amplicons may be reduced to about 100 μ L in the SpeedVac.

Library Quantification Supplies and Equipment

Item	Use/Notes
NEBNext Library Quant Kit for Illumina	Listed in supplies as New England Biolabs E7630L; RMK/CBFG notes indicate this is currently used instead of KAPA.
qPCR plates/tubes and seals	Used for library quantification.
Bio-Rad CFX qPCR instrument	Required for library quantification; Nextera workflow reserves BioRad CFX for library quantification steps.
Library quantification calculator/spreadsheet	Used to calculate final library concentration and pooling amounts.
DNA LoBind tubes	Used for library dilutions and pooled libraries.

MiSeq Sequencing Supplies

Item	Use/Notes
Illumina MiSeq Reagent Kit v2	Supplies list includes Illumina MiSeq Reagent Kit v2 #MS-102-2003.
MiSeq cartridge	Thawed before loading; CBFG SOP warns not to overheat cartridge and to check wells for crystals.
Flow cell	Loaded during MiSeq setup.
PR2 incorporation buffer	Loaded during MiSeq setup.
HT1 buffer	Used for denaturing/diluting libraries before loading.
PhiX Control v3	Used as sequencing control/spike-in; included in CBFG consumables list.
0.2 N NaOH	Used for library denaturation before loading.
Custom Read1, Read2, and Index sequencing primers	Loaded into cartridge wells for custom amplicon sequencing.
Long Pasteur pipettes	Used to mix custom primers in cartridge wells according to CBFG SOP.
Sample sheet CSV	Required for Local Run Manager/MiSeq run setup.
BaseSpace account	Required for run upload/backup; CBFG SOP emphasizes this as important for preventing data loss.

MiSeq and Data Equipment/Software

Equipment/Software	Use/Notes
Illumina MiSeq	Used for sequencing run; must be reserved through CBFG.
Local Run Manager	Used to set up sequencing experiment and sample sheet on instrument.
MiSeq Control Software	Used to start run and check run parameters.
Illumina Sequencing Analysis Viewer	Used to monitor run quality metrics.
BaseSpace	Cloud storage/backup for sequencing reads.
Lab/project data storage location	Final FASTQ files, sample sheets, metadata, and analysis files should be copied to the appropriate RMK Lab project folder.

Reservation/Coordination Checklist

Resource	Reservation/Coordination Needed
CBFG consultation	Notify CBFG/Andor approximately one week before sequencing.
Liquid-handling robot	Reserve through CBFG Calcium system.
Bio-Rad CFX qPCR instrument	Reserve for library quantification.
MiSeq	Reserve for cartridge loading and sequencing run.
SpeedVac	Reserve through CBFG Calcium system.
Thermocyclers	Confirm availability before PCR setup.
Fume hood	Confirm availability before phenol-chloroform extraction.

Appendix 2: Ordering sequencing supplies

Copies ordering sheets:

https://drive.google.com/open?id=1mf0HUuv3U1MlrpXuG2XQk1pxhBLfxpo4&usp=drive_fs

*Note: must check current price on company website and update the order sheet prior to ordering.

PCR

1. Primers: <https://www.idtdna.com/> logon: morganr2/ Dxw7td1122 note: for purchasing you need a P.O. Number – Amy generates one for us yearly and we can use many times.
2. 96-well PCR plates: VWR® PCR Plates, 96-Well Standard Semi-Skirted, 0.20 ml, Clear (100/case); #83007-374
3. 96-well aluminum membrane sealing film: VWR #470347-462
4. 96-well heat seals: Azenta #4T1-0541; Fisher # NC2306755
5. Colorless GoTaq: GoTaq(R) G2 Hot Start Colorless Master Mix, 1,000 reactions Promega M7433
6. DNA water: Invitrogen™ Nuclease-Free Water (not DEPC-Treated), 10x50mL; Fisher # AM9937

LIBRARY PREP

1. Library Cleaning/Normalization: Charm Biotech #JN-120-10
<https://www.charmbiotech.com/PCR-Norm.htm>
2. Sequencing Libraries: Illumina MiSeq Reagent kit V-2 #MS-102-2003
3. Library quantification: NEBNext Library Quant Kit for Illumina, 500 reactions New England Biolabs, E7630L
4. DNA Low Bind Tubes: Eppendorf™ DNA LoBind™ Tubes, 1.5mL, pack of 250 Fisher # 13-698-791

OTHER PLASTICS

1. Rainin Electronic/multichannel/repeater pipettes
 - a) BIOTIX™ XTIP™ Rainin LTS Compatible Filter Low Retention Sterile Pipette Tips; 200uL pack of 960 Fisher # 12-111-362
 - b) BIOTIX™ XTIP™ Rainin LTS Compatible Filter Low Retention Sterile Pipette Tips; 1000uL pack of 960 Fisher # 12-111-364
2. Universal filter tips:

- a) 10 uL XL USA Scientific 1120-3710
 - b) 200 uL USA Scientific 1120-8710
 - c) 1000 uL USA Scientific 1126-7710
3. 8-tube PCR strips: USA Scientific 1402-2900

ALWAYS MAKE DETAILED NOTES IN YOUR LAB NOTEBOOK! THE MORE DETAILS THE BETTER!

Detailed Title: 16S rDNA (or Amplicon) NGS Sequencing on Illumina MiSeq: Library Generation, QC, Sequencing Acquisition, & RAW Reads Processing (Demultiplexing) on Instrument

Authors: Andor Kiss, Xiaoyun Deng (*modeled after the SOP from Schloss Lab¹*)

Original: November 9th, 2016

Last Edit: October 22, 2025

AIM OF THIS PROTOCOL:

The purpose of this protocol is to assemble into one master document the procedure for sequencing amplicons on the Illumina® Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) MiSeq platform. NGS is a massively parallel approach to sequencing DNA that enables one to sequence millions of different templates all at once using a relatively short-read (50 ~ 300 bp) technology. Computer programmes then can re-assemble the short-reads into complete sequences for downstream analysis. This particular protocol is CBFG-tailored version of the [Earth Microbiome Project \(EMP\)](#) 16S amplicon sequencing protocol. The EMP is based at Argonne National Laboratory under the direction of [Jack Gilbert](#).

We have provided a step-by-step approach to get you to the point where you can then analyse your data. We do not provide analysis guidelines, as those as rapidly evolving and under constant revision by the community.

BACKGROUND:

The construction of libraries outlined in this protocol is specific to the variable region 4 (V4) region of the 16S rRNA prokaryotic and archaeal sequences, widely used for taxonomic and phylogenetic identification both for Sanger and Illumina (NGS) based sequencing approaches. We make use of the CBFG's Eppendorf epMotion 5073m NGS liquid handling workstation and therefore have adapted all the protocols for 96 well microplates. We can, of course, use any plastics (labware) – however, new labware requires extensive troubleshooting and unless there is a significantly compelling reason, we ask that you use the recommended and tested labware(s).

The original EMP protocol papers were published in *ISME* (Caporaso, J.G., Lauber, C.L., Walters, W.A., Berg-Lyons, D., Huntley, J., Fierer, N., Owens, S.M., Betley, J., Fraser, L., Bauer, M., et al. (2012). Ultra-high-throughput microbial community analysis on the Illumina HiSeq and MiSeq platforms. *ISME J.* 6, 1621–1624.) and *PNAS* (Caporaso, J.G., Lauber, C.L., Walters, W.A., Berg-Lyons, D., Lozupone, C.A., Turnbaugh, P.J., Fierer, N., and Knight, R. (2011). Global patterns of 16S rRNA diversity at a depth of millions of sequences per sample. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA.* 108 Suppl, 4516–4522.). For detailed instructions, you'll have to download the supplemental material and go through that for details on the protocols (*i.e.* primer design, reagents, instrument settings).

¹ Kozich, J.J., Westcott, S.L., Baxter, N.T., Highlander, S.K., and Schloss, P.D. (2013). Development of a dual-index sequencing strategy and curation pipeline for analyzing amplicon sequence data on the MiSeq Illumina sequencing platform. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 79, 5112–5120.

Cost Estimate:

The following is a cost estimate (October 22nd, 2025) for in-house (MiamiU Researchers), when the labour is largely supplied by the laboratory in question. Because we are a training facility, we do not (*typically*) provide the labour for MiamiU researchers; however this can be arranged – labour costs are an additional \$2500 per run.

For external customers (those outside of MiamiU), we do take orders for sequencing and we feel our prices are very reasonable. Please make a formal request to <CBFG@MiamiOH.edu>.

In-House Consumables Estimate:

Item – Consumables	Cost (16S)
MiSeq v2 500 rxn Cartridge, Flow Cell, Incorporation Buffer (+ Dry Ice Shipping)	\$1,700.00
PhiX Control v3	\$60.00
16S/18S emp Rev Primers (96)	\$200.00
16S/18S emp For, Read1, Read2, Index (96)	\$15.00
GoTaq G2 HotStart Taq Polymerase (96 rxns @ 75 microl)	\$175.00
Just-A-Plate Normalisation (CharmBiotech)	\$75.00
Agarose Gel – Visualisation (10 ~ 20 random picks) – ***Optional	\$20.00
KAPA qPCR Quantitation	\$100.00
Robotics Tips (Filtre @ \$22 Rack)	\$200.00
96 well VWR Plates (@ 10 each)	\$40.00
30 mL Reservoirs (Reagents)	\$40.00
Filtre Tips for Loading	\$10.00
1.5 mL LoBND Eppendorf Tubes (dilutions)	\$2.50
Total	\$2,637.50
(Price per sample based on 96 samples)	\$27.47

Items in grey MUST be either supplied by each laboratory, or we will do the qPCR and charge each laboratory the fee listed. Items listed are “per-run” pricing, and do not take into account the initial acquisition cost.

The above price assumes that the investigator has pre-aliquoted the gDNA into a 96-well plate. Additional plates (multiples of 96 will incur **more cost indicated in BLUE**).

For example; the KAPA Universal Illumina Library Quantitation Kit is about \$750 for 100 rxns.

There are also alternate suppliers of Illumina Quantitation Kits (e.g. Promega, NEB).

DAY ONE (We provide a rough guide of "DAYS" for the novice; experienced users will likely shorten the number of days to about two)

Library Construction

- 1) Upon receipt of the 96 well DNA sample plate from customer inventory the plate by assigning it a number and entering the sample details into a spreadsheet. The numbering system should follow the following format:

<YEARMONTHDAY-INITIALS-PLATE#>

For example, for Andor J Kiss: **20250307-AJK-01**

Keep the 96 well Sample Plate in a -20°C Freezer (right hand CBFG Freezer; #C), or the chest freezer.

Click on Settings > Devices > Clean CAP > Turn on HEPA filter > THEN LOAD ROBOT!

- 2) Library Construction:

- (a) Set-up PCR amplification of the 16S rDNA region using the 515f/806r primer set. These are the "old" primers that the EMP (Earth Microbiome Project) (<http://gilbertlab.com/contact-us/>) pioneered. The GOLAY barcodes are on the REVERSE primer (Caporaso JG, Lauber CL, Walters WA, Berg-Lyons D, Huntley J, Fierer N, Owens SM, Betley J, Fraser L, Bauer M, Gormley N, Gilbert JA, Smith G, Knight R. 2012. Ultra-high-throughput microbial community analysis on the Illumina HiSeq and MiSeq platforms. *The ISME Journal [Internet]* 6:1621–1624. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/ismej.2012.8>). The current primer sets that is on the EMP website (<http://www.earthmicrobiome.org/emp-standard-protocols/16s/>) now use the modified 515f/806rB primer set and the GOLAY barcodes are on the FORWARD primer.

- (b) Most of the protocols are pre-programmed on the epMotion 5073m. The list of relevant programmes (in most likely use order) are:

Find the program you want in Application Editor: EMP Protocols (or ASK ANDOR)

- ① EMP Amplicon Protocol (I **III** the differences are in the PCR plates) **Use Protocol III for VWR plates**
- ② EMP Amp Post-PCR Protocol
- ③ EMP Amp SeqPool II

- (c) You will need the gDNA, the emp REV primer plate, the forward primer, G2 GoTaq Hot Start Master Mix (clear), or regular non-hot start, and ddH₂O. Essentially, you have a plate of gDNA and a plate of emp REV primers. One then combines the gDNA with the reverse primers and then you add the MasterMix (which is ddH₂O + FOR primer + G2 GoTaq® Hot Start Master Mix (clear)). Each reaction will be assembled as a 75 µL reaction and then split into 3 separate reactions into 25 µL.

This can be modified as necessary – meaning that many environmental samples require samples to be amplified in triplicate. However, for gut microbiome samples, it is usually not necessary to perform PCR in triplicate, usually just a single 25 µL reaction per sample will suffice.

Make sure all items for robot are always organized with A1 on top left corner

Thaw reverse primers (plates) only as advised by Andor

NOTE: You need to use the 5 uM reverse GOLAY primers (plates)

See notes at the end (pg 13) for Primer storage location and names (from CBFG)

(d) Set-Up for the reactions according to this table below – make enough of the MasterMix for 110 reactions instead of 96 reactions.

Component	One (1) Reaction (µL)	110 Reactions (µL)
GoTaq® G2 Hot Start Colorless Master Mix	37.50	4,125.00
FOR emp (515f) Primer (100 µM)	0.15	16.50
REV emp (806r) Primer [GOLAY] (5 µM)	3.00	330.00
Template (gDNA @ ~10 ng * µL ⁻¹)	3.00	330.00
ddH ₂ O	31.35	3,448.50
Total Volume	75.00	8,250.00

For the MasterMix, the Template and the REV primer (grey in table above) are already in the target plate. The MasterMix is therefore less 330 µL (Template) and 330 µL (REV primer) – a total of 660 µL.

MasterMix:

Component	Per Rxn (µL)	Per 110 Rxns (µL)
GoTaq® G2 Hot Start Colorless Master Mix	37.50	4,125.00
FOR emp (515f) Primer (100 µM)	0.15	16.50
ddH ₂ O	31.35	3,448.50
Total Volume	69.00	7590 (÷ 4 = 1898 per 2 mL tube)

Make MasterMix up in a 15 mL sterile falcon tube. Invert and/or vortex the tube several times to insure proper mixing prior to allocation into the 30 mL Reservoir.

Place master mix reservoir in slot 4 of C2 metal holder

The robot ALP for thermal control will automatically go to 4°C based on the programme. Make sure that the ACME 96 well block (brass coloured) is pre-chilled (they should always be stored in the 4°C fridge in the CBFG). **Use only eppendorf brand barrier tips (new) for all procedures – very important when doing PCR and multiple different templates (gDNA).**

- Robot: Tmx (2) means 2 sets
- Number of samples = 96 (or whatever sample count you have)
- Use required minimum volumes
- When setting up: Ignore for C2 (3 times)

Robot prompts: when the robot tells you a prompt, ALWAYS COMPLETE THE PROMPT THEN CLICK OK

(e) Once the PCR reactions are all aliquoted (75 μ L \div 3), 25 μ L per well in a total of three plates, seal the 96 well plates with a thermaseal film (e.g. PhenixResearch (Thomas Scientific) Products Cat#: LMT-THER-RTQ). Place the plates in an MJ Research thermal cyclers and use the following programme (from the EMP website): <16S_EMP> or <18S_EMP>

- (1) 94°C for 3 minutes
- (2) 94°C for 45 seconds
- (3) 50°C for 60 seconds
- (4) 72°C for 90 seconds
- (5) GOTO Step (2) for 34 Additional Times
- (6) 72°C for 10 minutes
- (7) 4°C for 5 minutes
- (8) End

(f) Once PCR is finished, use the epMotion robot to recombine the three plates (25 μ L) into one (75 μ L) using <EMP Amp Post-PCR>.

(g) As of 2018, we use the SequelPrep Normalisation Protocol for normalisation.

(h) As of 2022, we switched from TF SequelPrep to Just-a-Plate (Charm Biotech).

Once complete, transfer normalized product to VWR plate

DAY TWO

Agarose Gel Analysis & Normalisation

3) Prepare 1% TAE agarose gel (for ~20 samples + DNA ladders):

- 2 grams agarose + 200 mL 1x TAE buffer → mix gently.
- Melt in microwave in 20 second intervals; give a swirl in between.
- When fully melted add 3 μ L Ethidium bromide (10 mg * mL⁻¹).
- Set-Up gel tray with combs.
- Pour agarose and allow a minimum of one hour to cool.

4) Analyse 5 μ L of ten or twenty randomly chosen amplicons on the agarose gel.

5) Take an image with the AlphamagerHD and save the TIFF for analysis.

6) Use the Just-a-Plate (highly, highly recommended), use 20 ~ 50 μ L of the 75 μ L pooled amplicons for purification.

We use 20 uL to normalize

- Do the pipetting by hand using the RANIN multichannel pipettors.

We use 10 uL to pool

- After normalisation, have the robot pool 7.5 μ L of each normalised amplicon (library) into a 1.5 mL LoBND Eppendorf tube <EMP Amp SeqPool II>

Place LoBind tube in slot 1 of the metal holder C2 (sometimes in the refrigerator)

- Reduce the volume to about 100 μ L in the SpeedVac if need be.

NOTE: We use NEB Next Quant Kit now**DAY THREE**

Quantitate the Pooled Library Using the KAPA qPCR Illumina Universal Kit²

14) Set up KAPA reactions according to the [manufacturer](#). You will need to perform the assay in triplicate for each sample and for the STD CURVE. Because you cannot interpolate the data, your unknown (NGS library) *must* fall within the STD CURVE. In other words, make several dilutions (in triplicate) so that you don't have to repeat the entire assay – one cannot simply re-do the unknowns without also re-running all the standards (see Fig. 1 from KAPA Biosystems).

- Make a dilution for the amplicon library (dsDNA) in H₂O:

Dilution	Volumes & Procedure for Dilutions
1:100	1 µL dsDNA + 99 µL H ₂ O → 100 µL
1:500	1 µL of [1:100] + 4 µL H ₂ O → 5 µL
1:50,000	1 µL of [1:500] + 99 µL H ₂ O → 100 µL
1:100,000	5 µL of [1:50,000] + 5 µL H ₂ O → 10 µL

Only use dilutions like 1:1000, 1:5000, etc DO NOT USE dilutions 1:1500, 1:5500 the calculator does not understand it

NEB NEXT CALCULATOR LINK: <https://nebiocalculator.neb.com/#!/qPCRlibQnt>

Figure 1. Principle of the KAPA Library Quantification assay. A set of six pre-diluted DNA Standards (representing a 10-fold dilution series of a linear, 452 bp dsDNA fragment), as well as appropriately diluted library samples, are amplified by qPCR, using the KAPA SYBR® FAST qPCR Master Mix and primers based on the Illumina® P5 and P7 flow cell oligo sequences. The average Cq value for each DNA Standard is plotted against \log_{10} (concentration in pM) to generate a standard curve. The standard curve is used to convert the average Cq values for diluted library samples to concentration. This is followed by a size-adjustment calculation, to compensate for differences between the length of the DNA Standard and the average fragment length of the libraries. Finally, the undiluted or working concentration of each library is calculated. Please refer to the KAPA Library Quantification Kit Technical Data Sheet for a detailed protocol and data analysis guidelines.

- Set up KAPA qPCR reactions* for:
 - Standards 1 through 6
 - Unknowns (Amplicon Library) @ 1:50K and @ 1:100K dilutions
 - NTC = No Template Control

**Perform all samples (both STDs & UNKs) in triplicate*

² If you are pooling two different libraries, (i.e. two different amplicons; 16S & 18S), you should perform a KAPA quantitation on each of the libraries *separately* and then pool them together. When you pool them together, if the amplicons (apparent band size on the gel) are different sizes, the shorter one(s) will bridge amplify faster, so one should take that into account.

If you have more than one plate, you need to pool all plates and re-run the quantitation. Use the below link to measure pooling volumes. (Find info on next page)

Illumina Pooling calculator: <https://support.illumina.com/help/pooling-calculator/pooling-calculator.htm>

- For each 20 µL qPCR reaction:

Reagent	Volume (1 reaction)	Volume (30 reactions)
KAPA qPCR Master Mix	12 µL	360 µL
ddH ₂ O	4 µL	120 µL
Sample (STD or UNK)	4 µL	Add ONE-BY-ONE
Total Volume	20 µL	600 µL
		<i>(600 µL ÷ 30 rxns = 20 µL)</i>

- KAPA qPCR Thermal Cycling Parameters:

- (i) 95°C for 5 minutes
- (ii) 95°C for 30 seconds
- (iii) 60°C for 45 seconds & data acquisition (camera)
- (iv) Goto Step (ii), 34 more times (35 total cycles)
- (v) Melt curve 65°C → 95°C

PLATE LAYOUT for KAPA qPCR Illumina Library Assay:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	1:50K	1:50K	1:50K	1:100K	1:100K	1:100K	STD1	STD1	STD1	STD2	STD2	STD2
B	STD3	STD3	STD3	STD4	STD4	STD4	STD5	STD5	STD5	STD6	STD6	STD6
C	NTC	NTC	NTC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

- Once qPCR data has been acquired, check the MELT CURVE for adaptor dimers and/or short fragments (see Fig. 2 from KAPA Technical Guide).
- Data can be processed manually, or by using a pre-formatted MS Excel spreadsheet downloadable from KAPA website, or from CBFG FTP website.
 - URL: <https://www.kapabiosystems.com/document/kapa-library-quantification-data-analysis-template/?dl=1>
- Please read the instructions on the MS Excel spreadsheet **very** carefully and pay attention to the MACRO and make sure it updates as data is entered into the spreadsheet.
- Once the data is entered, use the quantitation as calculated by the spreadsheet.
- If there is more than one dilution (recommended); check to see how close each quantitation is to each other. If there are close, or they are “in-line” (the STD DEV isn’t too far away) with the mean STDs quantitation, then you should average them. However if one of the dilutions is too far away (looks wacky), you might want to be careful about taking the mean. Try to use the dilution(s) that are closest to the mean trend line (least STD DEV).

Illumina Pooling Calculator entry

Library plexity = number of plates/libraries

Do libraries have the same concentration? = different (unless they are exactly the same)

Unit of measurement of library = nM

(ALWAYS CHECK WITH ANDOR OR RMK)

Pooled library concentration = how much do you want the concentration for the final pool to be, generally ~ 2 nM (but should not be higher than the lowest concentration of a library)
 Example, if library 1 is 1.8 nM and library 2 is 1.5 nM the pooling concentration can be 1.5 nM but not 2 nM

Total Pool volume = what volume do you want the final pool to be? (check with Andor)

> Calculate

NOTE DOWN THE TABLE in your lab notebook

AT THIS POINT (IF YOU DO NOT ALREADY HAVE ONE) YOU NEED TO SIGN UP FOR AN ILLUMINA BASESPACE ACCOUNT IN ORDER TO LOAD AND RUN YOUR SAMPLES. BASESPACE IS ILLUMINA CLOUD STORAGE SYSTEM FOR ACQUIRED NGS DATA AND SERVES AS A BACKUP SYSTEM FOR YOU. THE ACCOUNT IS FREE AND YOU RECEIVE A FREE 1 TB OF ON-LINE STORAGE. FAILURE TO HAVE A BASESPACE ACCOUNT MAY RESULT IN A CATASTROPHIC LOSS OF YOUR RUN DATA.

THE CBFG IS **NOT RESPONSIBLE FOR YOUR DATA LOSS.**

BASESPACE URL: <http://www.illumina.com/>

DAY FOUR*Load Library on the MiSeq & Acquire NG Sequence Data*

- 15) Prepare (thaw) MiSeq Reagent Kit v2 – 500 reactions – (**Illumina Cat#: MS-102-2003**)
 - Take cartridge out of the -20°C freezer and thaw in lukewarm water up to level indicated on the side of the cartridge (or defrost it O/N at 4°C)
 - **DO NOT** overheat the cartridge to make it thaw faster – it is full of enzymes and you will damage the reagents.
 - It should take about one hour to thaw completely.

- 16) While the cartridge is thawing, Begin to thaw (a) HT1 buffer, (b) PhiX 174 v3 (loading control), (c) custom sequencing primers (Read1, Read2 and Index primers). The custom primers should all be at [100 mM].

- 17) Prepare fresh 0.2N NaOH from a 10N Stock (or else thaw an aliquoted 0.2N 1.5 mL tube)

- 18) Prepare the library for load → you will be loading 4 pM³ of library with a 10% PhiX spike-in, this gives you a 3.6 pM of library and 0.4 pM of PhiX spike-in total load. If you are using dual INDEX primers, or primers with random offsets in the pad, you *can* lower the PhiX spike-in.

In two separate tubes:

- To a 1.5 mL eppendorf tube, add 10 µL of library and 10 µL of 0.2N NaOH.
- To a 1.5 mL eppendorf tube, add 2 µL PhiX, 3 µL ddH₂O, and 5 µL of 0.2N NaOH.
 - Pipette each mixture (with a separate tip) up and down to mix. **N.B.:** NaOH concentration on the flow cell must remain under 0.001 N.
 - Adjusting the concentration of the NaOH used to denature the DNA to 0.1N may be necessary if the library starting concentration is 1 nM (unusual situation).
- Allow the tubes to incubate/denature the dsDNA at room temperature for 5 minutes. Immediately add 980 µL of ice-cold HT1 to the library tube, and 990 µL HT1 to the PhiX tube.
 - The resulting 20 pM PhiX can be frozen and used for subsequent runs for about two weeks.
- Use HT1 to further dilute both the library and PhiX to 4 pM for a v2 kit.
 - Can load up to 8 pM for a v3 kit → *However, version 3 chemistry not recommended as it tends to overcluster – decreasing data quality (Pat Schloss – personal communication).*

³Please make sure that you OPTIMISE the amount to be loaded. We have found that in many cases, in our laboratory, 4.0 pM for V2 kits is really, really pushing the envelope of maximum. If you *over-cluster* a run, most of the data will be useless. Better to *under-cluster* by a little and get useful data (albeit not as much as one could get for a maximal load), rather than lose all data.

RECOMMEND: While you wait for the final quantitation to finish, write down the calculation math in your lab notebook with a placeholder for unknown nM, so that it is easier when you get the unknown nM to plug in and do math. ALSO ADD the 5 min incubation step in your calculations so that you can check off as you prepare reagents

CBFG – Illumina MiSeq 16S Metagenomics Protocol

Example Library Dilution 90% Library / 10% PhiX (Your Numbers will differ for the [Library])

- (a) $(1.45 \text{ nM library} * 10 \mu\text{L}) + (0.2\text{N NaOH} * 10 \mu\text{L}) + 980 \mu\text{L HT1} = 14.5 \text{ pM Lib, } 0.002\text{N NaOH}$
- (b) $(14.5 \text{ pM library} * 275.86 \mu\text{L}) + 724.14 \mu\text{L HT1} = 4.0 \text{ pM library, } 0.00055\text{N NaOH}$
- (c) $[(10 \text{ nM PhiX} * 2 \mu\text{L}) + 3 \mu\text{L H}_2\text{O}] + (0.2\text{N NaOH} * 5 \mu\text{L}) + 990 \mu\text{L HT1} = 20 \text{ pM PhiX, } 0.001\text{N NaOH}$
- (d) $(20 \text{ pM PhiX} * 200 \mu\text{L}) + 800 \mu\text{L HT1} = 4.0 \text{ pM PhiX, } 0.0002\text{N NaOH}$
- (e) $(4.0 \text{ pM Library} * 900 \mu\text{L}) + (4.0 \text{ pM PhiX} * 100 \mu\text{L}) = \text{Overall Solution Loaded}$
- (f) Solution loaded is 4.0 pM overall: with a 3.6 pM Library (90%) concentration, 0.4 pM PhiX (10%) concentration, and an 0.000515N NaOH concentration.

You might consider HEAT denaturing the DNA + 0.2N NaOH prior to dilution, e.g. add 5 μL X nM LIB+ 5 μL X nM PhiX \rightarrow denture @ 95°C for 2 minutes, ice for 1 minute, then add dilution (HT1 Buffer) volume. However, heat denaturation is now discouraged by Illumina (officially).

- 19) You can either make up 1000 μL total volume and load 600 μL , or make up just a total volume of 600 μL (this is why there are some protocols that tell you to make 1000 μL vs 600 μL ; you will only every be loading 600 μL (of the 1000 μL). For a 10% PhiX, combine 540 μL of 4.0 pM Library and 60 μL 4.0 pM PhiX in a final tube. Vortex. Label the tube **LOAD**.
- 20) When the reagent cartridge has thawed, dry bottom with paper towel. Invert the cartridge repeatedly and then check that each well is thawed. You are looking for crystals (undissolved salts) in the large reservoirs. If not completely thawed, replace in lukewarm water until completely thawed – invert & re-check. The inversion of the cartridge also serves to mix the reagents, which MUST be done prior to running the MiSeq.
- 21) Set-Up the experiment using **Local Run Manager** – on instrument. The sample sheet required for running the Illumina MCS (MiSeq Control Software) is a simple <*.csv> comma separated value (text file).
- 22) We have already made an empty sample sheet for you. It is on the FTP server under the <MiSeq_Amplicon> directory as a <*.csv> file. Download it and open it using a spreadsheet programme.

23) Edit the greyed boxes below. You must enter **unique** sample IDs for each and every sample, as those will become the file names. Also please pay attention to entering the reverse compliment of the <INDEX> code ([GOLAY codes](#)). These can also be found on our FTP server for each of the plates.

	A	B	C	D
1	[Header]			
2	Experiment Name	Sample Experiment		
3	Date	MM/DD/YYYY		
4	Module	GenerateFASTQ - 3.0.1		
5	Workflow	GenerateFASTQ		
6	Library Prep Kit	Custom		
7	Index Kit	Custom		
8	Description	Insert Description Here		
9	Chemistry	Default		
10	[Reads]			
11		251		
12		251		
13	[Data]			
14	Sample_ID	Description	index	Sample_Project
15	UniqueSampleID	Description	RC_GOLAY_CODE	Unique_Project_Name
16				
17				
18				

24) If you do want to set-up the sample sheet via LRM, please choose <CUSTOM> as the library kit and enter the information as per above. DO NOT select any adapter trimming, nor any custom primers.

25) You must enter in all the samples and their INDEX codes. This will enable demultiplexing on the instrument and the uploading of the demultiplexed files to your BASESPACE account.

We no longer support single output file for manual demultiplexing.

25) It is a very good idea to power cycle the instrument before beginning a run.

- Use the “Manage Instrument” option → ReBoot

26) Unbox the Flow Cell and PR2 Incorporation Buffer (square) bottle – stored @ 4°C.

- Clean Flow Cell with ddH₂O from a squirt bottle, aiming on the surface downwards into a rinse reservoir. DO NOT squirt ddH₂O into the back rubber intake ports.
- Once the preservative has been rinsed from the Flow Cell, blot the Flow Cell on paper towel taking care not to scratch the optical surface of the flow cell. Then, using lens paper, and 70% EtOH, wipe the Flow Cell clean such that it is completely clear (optically) when held up to the overhead light.
 - Smearing and/or blemishes will interfere with the imaging process and cause failure.
 - Pay particular attention to residual ethanol in cracks and crevices.

Index primers (tubes) for cartridge loading are located in sets of 3 in the pink box in the freezer "C" n the CBFG

NOTE: primer names are subject to change; make a note of actual base pairs in your lab notebook and ALWAYS crosscheck!

22) Using a new 1000 µL pipette tip (blue or white) for each well, pierce the aluminum foil covering wells 12, 13, 14 and 17. When piercing each well, be sure to round out the foil to create the largest unhindered opening. Use one hand to do the piercing and rounding and use the other to hold down the MiSeq cartridge so as to ensure that the cartridge does not tip or is inadvertently spilt.

- **RECOMMENDATION:** *Rather than pierce all the foils required and then add the reagents, it is strongly recommended that you 'pierce as you go'. In other words, pierce foil of well 13 and then add reagent to well 13. Then, pierce foil of well 14 and then add reagent to well 14, and so forth...*

We load the **SAMPLE** at the end, **ALWAYS LOAD SAMPLE!!!!**

23) Load 600 µL of the **SAMPLE** (Library + PhiX mixture (e.g. 4 pM)) into well **17**.

24) Load 3(0) µL of the custom 10(0) µM **Read1** Sequencing Primer into well **12**.

- Using a sterile (autoclaved) long nosed (9") Pasteur pipette; mix the contents thoroughly.

25) Load 3(0) µL of the custom 10(0) µM **Index** Sequencing Primer into well **13**.

- Using a sterile (autoclaved) long nosed (9") Pasteur pipette; mix the contents thoroughly.

26) Load 3(0) µL of the custom 10(0) µM **Read2** Sequencing Primer into well **14**.

- Using a sterile (autoclaved) long nosed (9") Pasteur pipette; mix the contents thoroughly.

At this point, you should have the Sample Sheet finished, the cartridge loaded with your sample, including the custom sequencing primers (Read1, Read2 and INDEX), the Flow Cell cleaned and the PR2 Incorporation Buffer and the Waste Water bottle prepped.

Next few steps are done in the MiSeq Control Software (MCS).

The SEQUENCE icon should be in the center of the MiSeq Screen.

- 27) Follow the on screen instructions:
- Enter your BASESPACE information, NEXT.
 - Load the Flow Cell, wait for the RFID to be read, NEXT.
 - Load the PR2 Incorporation Buffer and Waste Bottle, lower sippers, RFID, NEXT.
 - Load the Reagent Cartridge, RFID, NEXT.
- 28) Ensure the MCS finds and recognizes the correct sample sheet and check to make sure that the run parameters are correct.
- MCS will give you the option of importing from LRM, or from a prepared file.
 - Choose the appropriate option.
- 29) Wait for the MiSeq to successfully perform its pre-run checks and press **START**.
- 30) Run Monitoring:
- a. Monitor the run periodically using Illumina Sequencing Analysis Viewer (SAV).
 - b. Ideal-ish parameters for a 80% 16S run:
 - (i) Cluster density 700-800 K * mm².
 - (ii) >85% clusters passing filter.
 - (iii) 10% aligned (amount of PhiX).
 - (iv) No spikes in corrected intensity plot.
 - (v) Final Q30 score of >90%.

DAY FIVE/SEVEN

- 32) Perform Post-Run wash.
- 33) Dispose of liquid waste and place spent reagent cartridge aside for disposal by EHS.
- 35) You will (should) now have two files (Read1, Read2) per sample on your basespace account under the RUN tab. Do not delete your basespace runs and be careful about transferring ownership.
- 36) For analysis, there is [mothur](#) or [QIIME2](#) or [CLC Genomics Workbench](#) (the CBFG has a paid copy of this software), or try the online webserver MOCHI [<https://academic.oup.com/-bioinformatics/article/38/18/4286/6649618>]

For Questions, Comments or Corrections, please send an eMAIL to: CBFG@MiamiOH.edu

NOTE: primer names are subject to change; make a note of actual base pairs in your lab notebook and ALWAYS crosscheck!

Forward primers (tubes) stored in a pink box in the standing freezer "C" in CBFG
 Forward primer: 16S called "16S FWD ISME"
 18S called "Illumina_Euk_1391 F"

Reverse primers (plates) located in the chest freezer in the CBFG

Reverse Primer sets
 16S: Set 1, Set 3, Set 5, Set 6
 18S: Set 2, Set 7, Set 8

APPENDIX 4

Modified by RMK lab (RP)

ALWAYS MAKE DETAILED NOTES IN YOUR LAB NOTEBOOK! THE MORE DETAILS THE BETTER!
Protocol for DNeasy PowerBiofilm Kit by Qiagen

Important points before starting

- Warm Solution MBL at 55 °C (water bath) for 5–10 min to dissolve precipitates prior to each use. * Prepare all tubes (label and setup) for extractions 1 day before the start of the procedure.
- Solution MBL should be used while still warm. * For this procedure, you need 5 x 2 mL tubes. The last tube should be labeled with the sample name on the top and side. And the extraction date on the side.
- Then turn the water bath to 65 °C (for step 4). * Other tubes CAN be sequentially labeled (1-20 etc) on the top and side
- If Solution MR has precipitated warm at 55 °C for 5–10 minutes.
- Shake to mix Solution PW before use.
- Use only PowerBiofilm Bead Tubes with this kit.
- Perform all centrifugation steps at room temperature (15–25°C).

NOTE: Record the amount of nuclease-free, sterile water added to each sample (into the tube containing the mat sample). Then follow the procedure below.

- Extremely dry mats, rehydrate by adding 500 µL of water (Add more if needed and vortex)
- Wet mats, do not add water
- Slightly wet mats, add 100 µL of water (Add more if needed and vortex)

PROCEDURE

1. Weigh out 0.10-0.15 g of biofilm material and place it into a 2 ml Collection Tube (provided). Centrifuge at 13,000 x g for 1min. Remove excess liquid using a pipette tip.

Note: Tare the collection tube on the weigh scale, then add biofilm material to get the appropriate weight.

Add less saturated samples (e.g., microbial mats) directly to the PowerBiofilm Bead Tube (For information on selecting the right amount of starting material, refer to the Troubleshooting Guide).

2. Resuspend the biofilm material in 350 µl of Solution MBL and transfer to the PowerBiofilm Bead Tube.

Note: For less saturated samples, add 350 µl of Solution MBL to the PowerBiofilm Bead Tube already containing the biofilm material.

3. Add 100 µl of Solution FB. Vortex briefly to mix.

4. Incubate the PowerBiofilm Bead Tube at 65°C for 5 min.

5. Bead beat the sample using PowerLyzer 24 Homogenizer

a. Identify each PowerBiofilm Bead Tube on **BOTH** the cap and on the side.

b. Properly balance the Bead Tubes in the tube holder of the PowerLyzer 24 and homogenize for 2 cycle at 3200 rpm for 30 s. (We use the same settings as in the RMK lab bead beater, ice between cycles)

c. Centrifuge the tube at 13,000 x g for 1 min. Transfer the supernatant to a new 2 ml Collection Tube (provided).

Note: Expect approximately **325**–400 µl of supernatant depending on sample material. If the volume falls below this range, use less starting material.

6. Add 200 µl of Solution IRS and vortex briefly to mix. Incubate at 2–8°C for 5 min.

Note: We use 200 µl of Solution IRS since the sample is known to contain large amounts of inhibitors. Refer to the Troubleshooting Guide.

7. Centrifuge the tube at 13,000 x g for 1 min.

8. Avoiding the pellet, transfer all of the supernatant to a 2 ml Collection Tube (provided).

Note: Expect approximately **375**–450 µl in volume depending on the sample material.

9. Add 900 µl of Solution MR and vortex briefly to mix.

Note: Refer to the start notes if the MR solution has precipitated

10. Load 650 µl of supernatant onto a MB Spin Column and centrifuge at 13,000 x g for 1 min. Discard the flow-through and repeat until all the supernatant has been processed.

11. Place the MB Spin Column into a clean 2 ml Collection Tube (provided).

12. Add 650 µl of Solution PW and centrifuge at 13,000 x g for 1 min.

13. Discard the flow-through and add 650 µl of ethanol (provided) and centrifuge at 13,000 x g for 1 min.

14. Discard the flow-through and centrifuge again at 13,000 x g for 2 min.

15. Place the MB Spin Column into a clean pre-labelled (FINAL) 2 ml Collection Tube.

16. Add 100 µl of Solution EB to the center of the white filter membrane.

17. Centrifuge at 13,000 x g for 1 min. Make sure the liquid is at the bottom of the tube.

18. Discard the MB Spin Column. The DNA is now ready for downstream applications.

§§ Charm Biotech

Just-a-Plate™ 96 PCR Normalization and Purification Kit

Store at room temperature

Product Contents and Storage

The components included with Just-a-Plate 96 PCR Normalization and Purification Kit are listed below. Upon receipt store all components at room temperature. Sufficient reagents are included to perform 2 X 96, or 10 X 96 DNA purifications and normalizations.

Product Catalogue #	JN-120-2	JN-120-10
Purification Scale	2 X 96	10 X 96
Binding Plate (BP5)	2 plates	10 plates
Binding Buffer (NB7)	4.4 ml	22 ml
Washing Buffer (WB2)	4.8 ml	24 ml
Elution Buffer (EB1)	9.0 ml	45 ml

Product Description

The Just-a-Plate™ 96 PCR Normalization and Purification Kit is designed and optimized for simple, fast, and high-throughput purification and normalization of PCR products. Up to 96 PCR reactions can be purified and normalized simultaneously in a 96-well microplate format. No spin-column, filter plate, silica membrane, or magnetic beads are needed for the clean-up and no vacuum or filtration steps are required in the process. Based on our Solid Surface Reversible Binding (SSRB) technology the Just-a-Plate system utilizes a 96-well plate with its surface coated with proprietary turbo-binders acting to selectively capture and efficiently bind DNA products from reaction mixtures. After performing PCR, DNA fragments will specifically interact with the turbo binders and bind to the surface of the wells in the presence of binding buffer. Primers, fluorescent dyes, nucleotides, and other contaminants will remain in solution. While using a fixed amount of turbo binder coated on the surface of the binding plate, the binding of the PCR products can be controlled in a certain amount by the coated capturing molecules. After washing the plate to remove unbound material, the purified and normalized DNA products can easily be eluted in 10 mM Tris buffer. The eluted products from each well are all in similar quantity, about 25 ng per well. This kit allows PCR product purification and normalization in a single step, eliminating the tedious manual normalization process after sample purification for sequencing sample preparation. The normalized and purified ready-to-use PCR products are ideal for use in automated next-generation sequencing reactions requiring the same amount of template inputs, offering superior data quality and read length.

Feature Highlights

Fast to perform: The whole process takes about one hour and but it only takes less than 10 minutes of hands-on time to purify and normalize 96 PCR samples.

Easy to handle: All procedures have been optimized with standard 96-well plates for ease-of-use. Elimination of multiple times of sample and buffer filtration in the sample binding and washing step associated with conventional membrane method makes whole procedure very easy to perform. No tedious manual normalization steps as DNA concentration determination, and sample dilution are required.

Reliable quality: Consistent well-to-well performance, reliable cross-contamination prevention procedure and unique solid-surface capture technology provide consistent yield at high DNA quality without any contamination.

Kit specifications: The kits are designed to purify and to normalize DNA fragment size of greater than 100 bps from PCR reaction with an input concentration range from 10 ng/μl to 200 ng/μl. The output from each well is about 25 ng after normalization.

Additional Materials Needed

- 96 – 100 % ethanol
- Multi-channel pipettor, tips, and reservoirs
- Adhesive foil plate cover or adhesive plastic plate cover
- Optional: Swing-bucket centrifuge capable of spinning microplates, such as Eppendorf Centrifuge 5804, Beckman GS-6, or Sorvall 6600

- Optional: Thermocycler
- Optional: Vortex

General Precautions

- This kit is for research use only. All due care and attention should be exercised in the handling of the kits.
- Wear a laboratory coat, disposable gloves, and eye protection when handling reagents and plate. Avoid ingestion and inhalation of reagents. Avoid skin contact with reagents in the kit. In case of contact, wash thoroughly with water. See Material Safety Data Sheets (MSDS) for emergency procedures in case of accidental contact or ingestion. MSDS information is available upon request.
- Always use proper aseptic techniques to avoid nuclease contamination when working with PCR and sequencing reactions and use only sterile, new pipette tips to prevent cross contamination.
- After elution of nucleic acid products from the wells, unused wells may be sealed with an adhesive foil cover and stored in the bag at room temperature for later DNA purification and normalization for up to 6 months.

Preparation before Starting

- To prepare working Washing Buffer (WB2), for JN-120-2 kit, add 19.2 ml of 100 % ethanol to the bottle and mix well. For JN-120-10, add 96 ml of 100% ethanol. (Mark bottle that ethanol has been added!) – Store at room temperature and use WB2 containing ethanol within six (6) months.
- After PCR, cooling the reaction to room temperature before purification.

Experimental Procedure

The protocol below is for the purification and normalization of DNA fragments from 20- μ l PCR mixtures using the Just-a-Plate 96 PCR Purification and Normalization Kit. The purification procedure may be scaled down (for example, 10- μ l) by proportionately adjusting all reagents throughout the procedure. Please call our technical support for more information.

Binding of PCR Products to Binding Plate

- ✓ 1. After completion of the PCR and equilibration at room temperature, transfer 20 μ l of each reaction mixture from the PCR plate to the Binding Plate (BP5) with a multi-channel pipettor. *(electronic)*
- ✓ 2. Mix the Binding Buffer (NB7) thoroughly by swirling the bottle. Add 20 μ l of Binding Buffer (NB7) to each sample well. Mix well with PCR products by pipetting liquid up and down 5 – 6 times. (Note: Avoid introducing bubbles while pipetting.) *(manual)*
- ✓ 3. Seal the Binding Plate (BP5) with an adhesive plate cover and incubate at room temperature for 30 – 60 minutes. (Note: The plate can be incubated overnight at room temperature if it fits your workflow.) *(left overnight)*
4. Remove the adhesive plate cover.
5. Remove the liquid from the Binding Plate. Choose one of the methods listed below to remove the liquid. (1) Decant the solution by quickly flipping the plate over a waste container and shaking briskly, then place the inverted plate on a stack of clean absorbent paper, such as Kimwipe® or paper towels, and tap the plate on the clean paper 3 – 4 times gently to remove as much liquid as possible; (2) Remove the solution by aspirating the solution from each well with a multi-channel pipettor. Be sure not to scrape the walls of the wells during aspiration as the products are bound to the walls. For consistency, we recommend to use a liquid handling robot, such as Biomek FXP from Beckman, EpMotion from Eppendorf or EVO Series from Tecan, for all pipetting work.

(Note: Please see below for sequential binding and elution, please use # (2) method listed above to transfer DNA solution to a new well. Since only about 25 -50 ng of PCR products is captured and purified from the PCR reaction from this procedure. Majority of PCR products is still in the solution after capture. If you want to keep the left-over PCR products, the remaining PCR products in the solution can be easily purified with our PCR purification kit (Cat No.JA-100-2). Please call us for more information.)

Washing Plate

1. Add 50 μ l Wash Buffer (WB2) containing ethanol to each well. Mix the solution by pipetting up and down 1 – 2 times. Incubate the plate for 30 seconds at room temperature. *→ wash mix with eppendorf P300*
2. Remove the Wash Buffer from the Binding Plate using one of the methods suggested in step 5 of Binding of PCR Products to Binding Plate above. *don't touch sides! use rainin P1200 repeater/multichannel*
3. Repeat steps 1 and 2 above once for a total of two washes.
4. After the final wash, blot the plate dry on a piece of clean absorbent paper and air-dry the plate in a lab hood for 5 – 10 minutes to remove any residual liquid. (Alternatively, put plate in a thermocycler or an air incubator and air-dry the plate without cover at 65 °C for 2 – 4 minutes.)

Eluting Products

PCR amplicons attached to the wall of the Binding Plate can be analyzed directly in the well by sequencing using a 20 – 50 μ l reaction volume without elution. If the DNA is to be eluted, use the procedure below

1. Add 20 - 40 μ l of Elution Buffer (EB1) into each well of the Binding Plate. (If higher concentration (such as, ~ 5 ng/ μ l) is preferred, add 10 μ l elution buffer.)

2. Seal the plate with a new adhesive plate cover and vortex the plate for 30 seconds. Centrifuge the plate at maximum speed briefly to collect all liquid at the bottom of the wells.
3. The eluted DNA fragments may be used immediately for downstream NGS application. Alternatively, the eluted products may be stored in the sealed plate at 4 ° C for short-term storage or at -20 ° C for long-term storage.

4. Transfer to VWR plate → pool in low bind tube.

DNA Quantitation and Downstream Application

The expected yield of DNA amplicons is about 25 ng per well normalized. You can use the purified and normalized DNA sample directly for your next-generation sequence (NGS) reactions or other applications. If determination of DNA yield is required, the quantity of purified DNA may be determined by fluorescent DNA assays, such as Picogreen assay. UV spectrophotometric measurement is not recommended since this method is inaccurate for low concentration DNA samples. The purified and normalized products are substantially free of contaminants such as salts, dNTP and primers, and can be used for next-generation sequencing analysis and other downstream applications in which high purity and normalized DNA templates are required.

Optional: Sequential Binding and Elution

If more than 25 ng of DNA amplicons are required, one way to improve the final yield is to do sequential binding and elution using the same DNA/binding buffer mixtures and elution solution. After the first binding of amplicons/binding solution mixtures to a well, transfer the same mixtures to another fresh well/plate for second binding at room temperature for 30 - 60 minutes. After washing the well, elute the DNA amplicons with the same elution buffer from the 1st well to obtain higher yield. Please call technical support for other options to increase the yield.

Recommendation for NGS workflow

If multiple samples (for example, 96 samples) need be sequenced with NGS, the following workflow is recommended: 1). After indexing PCR (or Adaptor-ligated DNA PCR Enrichment), use 10 µl - 20 µl reaction volume to do PCR product normalization with 20 µl elution volume with current kit. Note: If 50 bps – 100 bps long primer dimers exist in the indexing PCR, we recommend to use our Just-a-Plate 96 PCR Purification kit (JA-100-10) to remove these primer dimers first before using current kit. 2) Take 5µl – 10 µl aliquot from each normalized sample and combine together (if combine 5µl together for 96 samples, you will have 480 µl pooled PCR products). 3). Check pooled sample concentration: use 2 µl pooled sample to check concentration with Picogreen and Qubit or doing qPCR with DNA standard. Pooled samples may need be diluted or concentrated further. 4) Check pooled sample fragment size: run Agilent BioAnalyzer with 10 µl - 20 µl pooled sample to examine the pooled PCR product size. 5) If certain size range DNA sample needs to be obtained, Just-a-Tube (Just-a-Plate) Size-Selected PCR Fragment Purification Kit is recommended, use 250 µl pooled sample as input and elute the final purified PCR products with 20 -80 µl elution buffer. This process can further define purified PCR fragment size as well as concentrating pooled PCR samples for NGS. 6) ready for NGS service.

Troubleshooting

Problem	Cause	Solution
Poor Normalization	Inconsistent handling	Do not scratch the plate surface while pipetting. Be sure to put pipette tip at the exact bottom center of each well while aspiration. Avoid generating bubbles while pipetting. If possible, use a fine-sharp small opening pipette tip for aspiration to reduce scrapping. Using automated liquid handling device is recommended to improve pipetting consistency.
Low yield of product	Insufficient DNA input	Make sure the input DNA concentration is ≥ 10 ng/µl.
	Long primer dimers (≥ 70 bps) existed	Remove long primer dimers first using PCR purification kit.
	Short target DNA fragment	To improve short DNA fragment yield, after mixing Binding Buffer (NB7) with PCR products, spin the Binding Plate (BP5) for 3-5 minutes at 2000 rcf, then incubate at room temperature for 60 minutes before washing plate step.
	DNA degradation	Be sure to follow lab guidelines to prevent DNase contamination.
	Incorrect volume of Binding Buffer	For 10-µl PCR mixtures, add 10-µl Binding Buffer (NB7)